

ISic0415

I.Sicily inscription 0415

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Roma

Place of origin (modern)

Rome

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 249 + 280

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR146571

1. □:Syracusic adtributam, sed pertinens ad Romam□

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 266318

EDR 146571; 081204

EDCS 21900478

Bibliography

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